

Conference abstract

A methodology for the development of serious games for the cognitive stimulation of elderly people with mild cognitive impairment

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ABSTRACT

Mild cognitive impairment affects many older adults and can lead to severe dementia. Early detection and intervention are key to slowing its progression. Serious games offer a promising way to stimulate cognitive function. However, there is a lack of clear methodologies for developing effective serious games for cognitive stimulation. In this paper, we introduce a methodology for developing serious games to help people with mild cognitive impairment. We also include a case study of this methodology through the development of a serious game that underwent usability testing with older adults. The obtained results provide evidence that, by following the proposed methodology, it is possible to develop serious games that are well received by the target population.

Keywords: serious games, cognitive impairment, cognitive stimulation

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